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3 **MINI-REVIEW**

4 **Microbial genomics, transcriptomics and proteomics: new discoveries in decomposition**
5 **research using complementary methods**

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9
10 **Abstract**

11 Molecular methods for the analysis of biomolecules have undergone rapid technological
12 development in the last decade. The advent of next-generation sequencing methods and
13 improvements in instrumental resolution enabled the analysis of complex transcriptome,
14 proteome and metabolome data, as well as a detailed annotation of microbial genomes. The
15 mechanisms of decomposition by model fungi have been described in unprecedented detail by
16 the combination of genome sequencing, transcriptomics and proteomics. The increasing
17 number of available genomes for fungi and bacteria shows that the genetic potential for
18 decomposition of organic matter is widespread among taxonomically diverse microbial taxa,
19 while expression studies document the importance of the regulation of expression in
20 decomposition efficiency. Importantly, high-throughput methods of nucleic acid analysis used
21 for the analysis of metagenomes and metatranscriptomes indicate the high diversity of
22 decomposer communities in natural habitats and their taxonomic composition. Today, the
23 metaproteomics of natural habitats is of interest. In combination with advanced analytical
24 techniques to explore the products of decomposition and the accumulation of information on
25 the genomes of environmentally relevant microorganisms, advanced methods in microbial
26 ecophysiology should increase our understanding of the complex processes of organic matter
27 transformation.

28
29 **Keywords**

30 Decomposition . Genomics . Metagenomics . Metatranscriptomics . Metaproteomics .
31 Saprotrophic fungi and bacteria

32

33 **Introduction**

34 Recently, rapid technological improvements have allowed the development of molecular
35 methods for the analysis of biomolecules. In particular, the advent of next-generation
36 sequencing methods enabled the scientific community to reduce the costs of large-scale
37 sequencing (Glenn 2011; Mardis 2011), and increases in instrumental resolution enabled the
38 analysis of complex proteome and metabolome data (Keiblinger et al. 2012; Wallenstein et al.
39 2013).

40 The potential of these methodological developments is demonstrated by advances in
41 decomposition research. Microbial decomposition receives extraordinary attention for two
42 major reasons: (1) on the level of individual microorganisms, it is driven by the biotechnological
43 need to find microorganisms or enzymes for lignocellulose transformation useful for the
44 production of biofuels, for example, and (2) the interest in complex decomposition processes in
45 the environment by the fact that decomposition represents an important part of the global
46 carbon cycle and affects global climate change through CO₂ release rates. The applications,
47 results and present possibilities of these complementary omics methods in the study and
48 understanding of microbial decomposition are highlighted in this review, focused mainly on
49 fungi and fungal decomposition.

50

51 **Omics methods for the exploration of decomposition by individual microorganisms**

52 In the early 2000s, after decades of research on fungal decomposition using physiological and
53 biochemical methods, the picture of decomposition pathways was detailed for a limited number
54 of model organisms, especially wood-rotting fungi. There was a good knowledge of the enzymes
55 produced by individual fungi, the corresponding genes and their regulation including their
56 activity on lignocellulose (Decelle et al. 2004; Guettler et al. 2003; Martínez et al. 2005). The
57 biochemical exploration of decomposition-related enzymes allowed informed conclusions about
58 the decomposition potential of individual fungi and the properties of their enzymes (Baldrian
59 2006; Lynd et al. 2002; Baldrian et al. 2008). This knowledge was rapidly advanced in subsequent
60 years, thanks to the novel possibilities associated with genomics, transcriptomics and
61 proteomics. The *Phanerochaete chrysosporium* genome sequence published in 2004 revealed

62 for the first time the impressive complexity of the array of genes encoding secreted oxidases,
63 peroxidases and hydrolytic enzymes that cooperate in wood decay (Martinez et al. 2004).
64 Analysis of the complete genome sequence of *Postia placenta* made it possible to compare the
65 gene pools of ligninolytic (white-rot) and cellulolytic (brown-rot) fungi and to define the genetic
66 features that distinguish these two ecophysiological groups (Martinez et al. 2009).

67 Comparisons of genome sequences make it theoretically possible to define the physiological
68 potential of individual fungal taxa, taxonomic groups or ecophysiological groups. In this way, the
69 analysis of fungal genomes revealed the presence of multiple multi-copper oxidases (the group
70 of enzymes including laccases) in different ecophysiological groups of fungi, suggesting that they
71 fulfil a wide variety of functions (Baldrian 2006; Hoegger et al. 2006; Kües and Rühl 2011). The
72 redundancy of extracellular enzyme families in fungal genomes was demonstrated to be typical
73 for ligninolytic peroxidases and hydrolytic enzymes (Eastwood et al. 2011; Žifčáková and
74 Baldrian 2012). The presence of multiple gene copies is most likely a result of the complex
75 regulation of expression that is frequently observed (Eastwood et al. 2011; van den
76 Wymelenberg et al. 2011), but it also reflects the evolutionary history of fungi and the events in
77 evolution that led to the development of specific ecophysiological groups of fungi (Floudas et al.
78 2012; Zhao et al. 2013). Most importantly, the combination of genome sequencing and
79 comparative transcriptomics shows that the presence of genes in genomes and their numerical
80 abundance in individual gene families are insufficient to estimate the potential of individual taxa
81 to produce corresponding genes and perform efficient decomposition of individual compounds.

82 Secretomes, the pools of secreted proteins, were obtained from *P. chrysosporium* grown on
83 wood by 2-D electrophoresis followed by mass spectrometry. The pool of secreted proteins,
84 mainly represented by oxidases and glycosyl hydrolases, was described in detail on the
85 background of the available genome sequence and indicated complex regulation patterns of
86 protein synthesis (Abbas et al. 2005; Ravalason et al. 2008; Sato et al. 2007). In comparison, the
87 information from proteomes of fungi without genome sequences was moderate (Zorn et al.
88 2005) due to the limited ability to assign the detected proteins to known genes. The advance of
89 next-generation sequencing methods shifted the preference from proteome to transcriptome
90 analysis. The analysis of tens of thousands of sequences transcribed by *P. chrysosporium*
91 indicated the relative importance of individual gene products for decomposition (Sato et al.
92 2009). As an alternative, transcriptomes of genome-sequenced fungi can be analysed by RNA
93 hybridisation with probes targeting functional or hypothetical genes. The results obtained from
94 *P. chrysosporium* using microarray analysis combined with proteomics indicated the importance
95 of certain oxidative enzymes and suggested the important role of many new proteins of

96 unknown function, underscoring the complexity of lignocellulose degradation (van den
97 Wymelenberg et al. 2009).

98 At present, quantitative proteomic techniques such as iTRAQ (Isobaric Tags for Relative and
99 Absolute Quantitation) and LC-MS/MS reveal a picture of the quantitative composition of fungal
100 proteomes that represent a better proxy of actual decomposition processes than do expression
101 studies. This technique, based in the labeling of peptides from protein digestions with isotope-
102 coded covalent tags of varying mass, was used to quantify the secretome of *P. chrysosporium*.
103 During the growth on cellulose, *P. chrysosporium* produces primarily endoglucanases,
104 exoglucanases, β -glucosidases and cellobiose dehydrogenase, suggesting both hydrolytic and
105 oxidative cellulose degradation. When lignin was used as a major carbon source, oxidative
106 enzymes such as copper radical oxidase, isoamyl oxidase, glutathione S-transferase, thioredoxin
107 peroxidase, quinone oxidoreductase, aryl alcohol oxidase, pyranose 2-oxidase, aldehyde
108 dehydrogenase and alcohol dehydrogenase were highly expressed (Manavalan et al. 2011).
109 Transcriptomic studies assisted in the elucidation of the molecular differences in the
110 composition and regulation of the decomposition machinery of various wood-rotting fungi
111 (Eastwood et al. 2011; van den Wymelenberg et al. 2010). These types of studies also revealed
112 that decomposition abilities differ among ectomycorrhizal fungi symbiotic with plant roots.
113 While *Laccaria bicolor* is a less efficient decomposer than related saprotrophic taxa (Martin et
114 al. 2008), *Paxillus involutus* is able to substantially decompose organic matter using a unique
115 enzymatic system (Rineau et al. 2012, 2013). Moreover, transcriptomic analysis has been used
116 for exploring the cellulolytic capacity of *Trichoderma reesei* on lignocellulose biomass, providing
117 the knowledge for the development of effective methods and adequate conditions for biofuel
118 production (Bischof et al. 2013). Biochemical exploration of fungal cultures also led to the recent
119 discovery of novel enzymes or better descriptions of those with previously unknown function.
120 This is the case for novel fungal peroxidases (the dyedecolorizing peroxidases) and unspecific
121 peroxygenases (Hofrichter et al. 2010). The exploration of fungal genomes demonstrated that
122 these novel oxidative enzymes are present in several species of the wood-rotting Polyporales
123 (Ruiz-Dueñas et al. 2013). Biochemical exploration demonstrated that cellulose cleavage by the
124 enzyme that was formerly described as glycosyl hydrolase GH61 (recently reclassified as
125 auxiliary activity family 9, AA9) is not based on hydrolysis but on the reaction of the
126 polysaccharide with molecular oxygen, and the enzyme is thus polysaccharide monooxygenase
127 (Beeson et al. 2011). The AA9 monooxygenase actually belongs to the most widespread enzyme
128 family active in cellulose degradation, harboured in the genomes of saprotrophic and parasitic
129 fungi as well as the mycorrhizal symbionts of plant roots (Žifčáková and Baldrian 2012).

130 Moreover, transcriptomic studies show that polysaccharide monooxygenases are heavily
131 produced during growth on wood by both white-rot and brown-rot fungi (Eastwood et al. 2011;
132 MacDonald et al. 2011) and may perhaps be responsible for the fast degradation of cellulose by
133 the latter.

134 Although the involvement of bacteria in decomposition processes has attracted much less
135 attention than that of the fungi, the fact that more than 1,500 bacterial genomes are available
136 compared to just over 100 fungal genomes (Větrovský and Baldrian 2013; Zhao et al. 2013)
137 represents an important advantage for genome comparisons in the prokaryota. Recently,
138 studies indicated that there is a widespread potential in multiple bacterial phyla to decompose
139 cellulose or to feed on its degradation products (Berlemont and Martiny 2013). In some bacterial
140 strains, such as *Streptomyces*, the biomass-degrading activity was comparable to a cellulolytic
141 enzyme cocktail from the fungus *T. reesei* (Takasuta et al. 2013). Zimmerman et al. (2013)
142 analysed more than 3,000 annotated bacterial genomes looking for potential production of
143 extracellular enzymes involved in nutrient cycling and decomposition of organic matter. In their
144 study, phosphatases, chitinases and N-acetylglucosaminidases were found in nearly half of the
145 genomes analysed. The relative ease of obtaining and annotating genome sequences of bacteria
146 helped to characterise four cellulolytic bacteria associated with woodwasps with respect to their
147 lignocellulose decomposition potential (Adams et al. 2011).

148 The integration of resources from genome sequencing projects covering both the prokaryotic
149 and eukaryotic microorganisms and exploration of individual genes enabled the establishment
150 of curated databases covering either a wide range of genes, such as the M5 non-redundant
151 protein database (M5Nr; Wilke et al. 2012) or Pfam (Punta et al. 2012) or specific groups of
152 functional genes including those for carbohydrates—CAZy (Cantarel et al. 2009) and lignin-
153 degrading enzymes—FOLY (Levasseur et al. 2008). The database creators started an important
154 work on the classification and categorisation of genes and proteins based either on their 3- D
155 structure (e.g. CAZY) or sequence features (e.g. M5Nr). Although this represents an important
156 step forward to the understanding of both the gene evolution and the genomic potential of
157 individual microorganisms, it has to be noted that the content of genes is not a direct predictor
158 of decomposition abilities.

159

160 **Exploration of microbial decomposition in complex environments**

161 Understanding decomposition in the environment, especially in plant litter and soil, was
162 previously limited to the knowledge of enzyme activities that can be detected in environmental

163 samples and studies measuring decomposition rates of natural compounds, for example, using
164 respirometry or incubation of litterbags. There was also limited knowledge on enzyme activities
165 in environmental isolates of microorganisms.

166 With the accumulation of gene sequence data for decomposition-related enzymes in public
167 databases, it became possible in the late 2000s to design degenerate primers capable of
168 amplifying partial sequences of decomposition-related genes from a wide range of fungi. This
169 made it possible to detect genes and transcripts encoding laccase and cbhl exocellulase from
170 forest floor DNA and RNA (Edwards et al. 2008; Luis et al. 2005). Subsequently, the diversity of
171 multiple oxidative and hydrolytic enzymes was demonstrated in forest topsoil
172 metatranscriptomes (Kellner and Vandenberg 2010). The combination of targeted
173 metatranscriptomics with next-generation sequencing and stable isotope probing allowed for
174 estimations of the numbers of exocellulase genes present in forest litter and soil and the
175 percentage of genes being transcribed. The results show that forest litter and soil harbours
176 several hundreds of cbhl genes, of which 25–40 % are expressed at the same time (Baldrian et
177 al. 2012; Štursová et al. 2012).

178 While targeted metatranscriptomics can be used to explore the diversity of individual genes,
179 analyses of complete metatranscriptomes make it possible to identify which genes or gene
180 families are responding to a given environment. The first general metatranscriptomic studies
181 showed the possibility of retrieving and characterising eukaryotic genes for decomposition from
182 soil (Bailly et al. 2007) and also the potential of using RNA for the simultaneous analysis of the
183 structure and function of active microbial populations in soils (Urich et al. 2008).
184 Metatranscriptomic exploration of eukaryotic genes in spruce and beech litter demonstrated
185 that extracellular decomposition-related enzymes represent <1 % of all expressed sequences
186 and that multiple families of oxidases and hydrolases are produced (Damon et al. 2012).
187 Although the assignment of environmental transcripts to the Ascomycota or the Basidiomycota
188 can be achieved for several genes, for a closer taxonomic assignment of individual genes to their
189 fungal producers, it is necessary to analyse more fungal genomes, especially of the taxa
190 inhabiting litter and soil (Marmeisse et al. 2013).

191 Metaproteomics was first developed for environments of limited complexity, such as
192 contaminated groundwater (Benndorf et al. 2007) or co-cultures of individual microbes
193 (Schneider et al. 2010). Later, in conjunction with the increased amount of information available
194 in public protein and DNA databases, it was possible to use this technique in a complex
195 substrate. The analysis of the proteome of decomposing litter showed the involvement of a

196 complex community of various eukaryotes and bacteria in decomposition (Schneider et al. 2012)
197 and indicated the successive changes of the decomposer community that were later confirmed
198 by the metagenomic analysis of the litter-associated fungal community and by enzyme activity
199 measurements (Voříšková and Baldrian 2013).

200 Since the advance of the genomics, transcriptomics and proteomics of individual
201 microorganisms and their complex communities, these approaches have dramatically increased
202 our understanding of decomposition (Table 1). Recently, these methods have begun to be
203 complemented with advanced analytical methods, such as analytical pyrolysis or mass
204 spectrometry-based analysis of metabolism of complex compounds (metabolomics). Some of
205 these methods have been used to study plant litter (Šnajdr et al. 2011; Valášková et al. 2007;
206 Wallenstein et al. 2010, 2013) and have helped to describe chemical composition changes at a
207 high resolution.

208 At the moment, these methods are able to identify the trends in decomposition of various
209 substances and to indicate similarities or differences in decomposition patterns among
210 individual microbial taxa or microbial communities inhabiting various environments (Valášková
211 et al. 2007; Wallenstein et al. 2013).

212

213 **Future trends and directions**

214 In the future, we can expect that the combination of these advanced analytical methods with
215 the metatranscriptomic and metaproteomic approaches will link the activity of microbial
216 communities and their individual members with biochemical processes in the complex natural
217 environment. Despite progress in the molecular methods, the understanding of environmental
218 processes will never be complete if it is not accompanied by the isolation and characterisation
219 of individual microbial taxa. This task is both laborious and technically demanding, and it should
220 receive much more attention from microbial ecologists than it currently does. However, if
221 successful, the exploration of genomes and transcriptomes combined with physiological
222 research on relevant environmental taxa will represent a significant impetus for understanding
223 the data from complex habitats provided by metagenomics and metatranscriptomics.

224

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229

230 **Conflict of interest**

231 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

232

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